

DESIGN EXPLORATION OF MULTI-LAYER SANDWICH STRUCTURES SUBJECTED TO TRANSVERSE LOADING

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Keywords: Composite Sandwich Structure, Multi-Layer Sandwich, Flexural Testing, Virtual Testing

ABSTRACT

Composite sandwich panels are conventionally made with a single core and two facesheets. Stacked sandwiches are prevalent where there is a demand for higher energy absorption. In this contribution, the core is divided into two equal parts and assembled with a thin inner plate from the same facesheet material forming a dual stacked sandwich panel. The force-displacement characteristics of single-cored (SC) and double-cored (DC) sandwiches under static loads were assessed through the experimental campaign. Under line-load, out-of-plane compression and point load the DC displayed enhanced force resistance of 11%, 29% and 41% in their peak loads and increased energy absorption of 42%, 51% and 44% respectively.

1 INTRODUCTION

Sandwich materials are widespread where high specific strength, stiffness and energy absorption capabilities are desired. Sandwiches are conventionally made with thin face sheets which are separated from the neutral axis by a thick soft core. The primary role of the facesheets is to carry in-plane and flexural loads with soft core being predominantly loaded in shear. Among different types of core materials available, hexagonal cellular cores like Nomex™ are prevalent in aviation because of their fire-resistant properties.

Several deviations from the conventional sandwich architecture are spread throughout literature to achieve enhancing specific aspects. Among which stacked sandwiches or cores [1, 2] or sandwich structures with multiple cores [3, 4] are sought often for their capability to resist medium to high-velocity impacts by staged energy absorption. Another tangential exploration by several researchers was enhancing the elastic properties of cellular sandwiches by filling with low-density foam [5].

Optimized design and continuous improvement of sandwich structures were made possible with the understanding of damage and failure modes induced [7, 8]. It was identified that the damage is initiated by either one of or a medley of core buckling and core crushing, matrix cracking, delaminations in facesheet or debonding in facesheet/core interface or fibre breakage in facesheets. These damage initiations eventually lead to failure of structure through core shear yield/fracture or facesheet cracking or overall core crushing depending on the load type. The shear stiffness of the post-buckled core reduces significantly between 40-60% of the pristine core at particularly lower loads, limiting their full potential realization [6]. Since the post-buckling is the design basis for many aerospace structures, enhancing their damage tolerance is highly desirable. From the knowledge of sandwich structures established in the literature, it is foreseen that the multi-layered sandwiches will help enhance their realization.

In this study, double cored (DC) sandwich is benchmarked against single cored (SC) sandwich for different types of static loading. Hedayati [9] studied the effect of using an "inner plate" on the resistance of sandwiches against bird strikes and observed mid-position could be the optimum position for excellent damage tolerance. Even though the above conclusion was drawn for dynamic loading, the inner plate located at mid-plane was also adopted here. Such a constraint helps with easier comparison against the SC since the stiffness contribution provided by the additional layers to overall stiffness is negligible because of the proximity of the inner plate to the neutral axis.

Different types of test methods are used to elucidate the delineated damage initiation and failure modes on a coupon level. Either three-point or four-point flexural testing is used to determine the core

shear properties [10]. Under shear loading, few core walls buckles initially followed by core shear yielding and fracture of the Nomex paper [6]. Flatwise compressive tests [11] are used to determine their critical load carrying capability, where the cores are subjected to planar compression across all the cells. Under out-of-plane compression, the failure mode is initiated by the cell wall buckling followed by overall crushing [12]. Quasi-static indentation tests are used to gauge a sandwich structures response to point load in a more controlled manner, where the interplay of all above-mentioned damage and failure modes are common [8].

Multi-layered sandwiches are not sought after for statically loaded structures due to their complexity of manufacturing. With the advent of additive manufacturing and automated fibre placement (AFP) combined with robotic manufacturing, difficulties associated so far will diminish eventually. Other than their perceived enhanced damage tolerant behaviour, thinner cores will be particularly advantageous mainly due to,

- Core thickness was identified to be an important parameter [13] to reduce the pressure load and consequently the crack front loading in a de-bonded sandwich from ground-air pressurization cycle, and
- Filler materials like epoxy void-filling compound are easy to be filled in smaller cellular cores than larger ones.

The current article is organized as follows: Initially brief description of sandwich coupons is provided, followed by testing methodologies. Secondly, a short description of the numerical model associated with one of the tests is provided, followed by comparison with experimental and numerical results. Finally, the conclusions drawn are discussed.

2 MATERIALS AND TEST METHODS

2.1 Experimental specimens and Test methods

The facesheets were made from 4 plies of Axiom AX5112-T plain weave carbon fibre pre-preg with a cured ply thickness of 0.2mm and the core was Nomex based Hexcel A1-64-13 honeycomb. Facesheets are firmly adhered to the core with Redux 330 adhesive film. The whole stacking arrangement is co-cured in an autoclave. Facesheets were sandwiched to 25mm core for the single cored specimens. The double cored specimens are similar to SC with the difference being the two 12.5mm core are separated by a single ply of ± 45 orientation. The cross-sectional architecture of all the SC and DC are similar with differences only in planar dimensions. The planar dimensions of specimens are as follows: 250 x 50mm for three-point bending test (TPBT), 50 x 10mm for flatwise compression tests and 100 x 100mm for quasi-static indentation tests.

The TPBT were conducted on Instron with a span distance of 150mm placed on 10mm diameter roller support. For the quasi-static indentation, the sandwich specimens were supported by two bolted two steel planks with a circular cut-out of 76.4mm indented with 14mm dia hemispherical indenter. All the tests were conducted at 3mm/s loading rate.

2.2 Numerical model description

Finite element based numerical models were built for the TPBT experiments in Abaqus/Standard 2017 to complement the experimental results only in the linear regime. Facesheets were modelled as continuum shell (SC8R) with the homogenised orthotropic elastic material model using the material data supplied by the manufacturer. Geometrically exact (perfect hexagon) honeycomb core was modelled with conventional shell elements (S4R) utilising orthotropic elastic-plastic material model (orthotropic ratio=1.3) with properties obtained from [14]. The model was built with the single and double wall average thicknesses of the cell walls measured from microscopic observations. Nomex cell walls despite being a multi-layer composite structure (resin-paper-resin) is homogenised into an orthotropic single layer due to its lower computational requirements.

The FE model described above is the component output created by the parametric study script created using Python which is being driven by the multi-objective optimisation tool, ISight. The model creation script takes cell width, core height and middle layer location as input from the driver and creates single and double cored FE input files for Abaqus. The model was created in the above manner so that building

block validation will be employed in future to perform comprehensive investigation of the influence of parameters.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section summarizes the experimental and numerical results together with the insights gleaned from the cross-sectional observations of the failed specimens.

3.1 Short beam three-point bending

From the TPBT experiments (Figure 2a), it is evident that the numerical models were able to estimate closely the initial stiffness and the dual-core sandwiches perform better under the shear loads. Since, only the linear portion of the load-displacement response is pertinent to the current analysis, 1.4kN is applied as the target load in FEM.

Due to the soft nature and lower yield strength of the core, plastic cell wall buckling, and shearing occurs at a significantly lower force level compared to the peak load magnitudes [8]. These damage modes were not possible to be detected by the experiments due to their relatively low energy dissipation levels. Similar to critical buckling estimation using bifurcation of load-displacement values in a non-linear buckling analysis, load-nodal rotation sum criteria was reported to be apt for assessing the shear behaviour of honeycomb cores [14, 15]. Nodal vector sum criterion was used to assess the shear stability of the SC and DC sandwiches, in which the absolute sum of nodal rotations in all the three directions of all the honeycomb nodes was monitored with the applied force. Any significant deviation or bifurcation would mean that the buckling configuration of the cell walls had changed.

From Figure 2b, the configuration of SC varies notably on more instances than the MC, especially around 0.9kN, whereas MC displays no such behaviour. The highlighted region in Figure 2b signifies that an increased number of cell walls are buckling in SC than the MC. In terms of peak loads, MC marks ~11% increase over the SC. Whereas, 42% higher energy absorption in the MC, which is calculated through the area under curve until the maximum displacement recorded in SC (~8mm). Force-displacement progression in the MC is more gradual with lesser number of load drops when compared with SC. It is hypothesised that this gradual progression arises because the cell walls of the one of the core is in the middle of the other when viewed from the top.

Figure 1: a) Numerical model of DC three-point bending specimen, (Inset) Microscopic image of Nomex honeycomb cell wall which is approximated to perfect hexagon in FE.

Figure 2: a) Experimental and numerical comparison of force-displacement values from three-point bending. b). Force-nodal rotation values obtained from numerical models

3.2 Flatwise compression

Figure 3a shows the load-displacement response of single and multi-core under flatwise compressive loads. Under flatwise compression, the cell walls of the cellular cores buckle progressively. Upon reaching the peak load, the cell walls collapse globally with a reduction in core height, which is marked by a sharp load drop. Upon further loading past the peak load, the cell walls continue to crush and densify, as reported in [12]. The force-displacement response of the DC is identical to the SC until the first load drop. As reported by Zhou et al., [2] the core failure is not symmetric, one of the cores fails prior with the second core remaining largely intact. This behaviour is hypothesised that it could be because the microscopic imperfections of one of the cores is higher than the other. Akin to TPBT, the peak load of the DC is $\sim 29\%$ larger than the SC and 51% more energy absorption. Another striking feature of DC is the second peak, which is almost twice the first peak load.

Figure 3: a) Nodal rotation magnitudes at 1kN in Single Core (left) and Double Core (right). Rotations (UR) are scaled (x3) for better visibility and both SC and DC share same colour scale.

Figure 3: a) Experimental and numerical comparison of force-displacement values from flatwise compression. b). Cross-sectional behaviour after first peak load of SC (top) and DC (bottom)

3.3 Quasi-static indentation

Single Cored (SC) and Double Cored (DC) sandwiched specimens prior to indentation and cross-sections of the indented specimens are shown in Figure 4a, b and c. Figure 4d shows the load-displacement response of single and multi-core under quasi-static indentation. From both the indented specimens it is apparent that the damage is localized to indenter periphery as expected. The initial contact stiffness of both the tested are similar emphasizing it was dominated majorly by the top face sheet regardless of core morphology. The force gradually increases until a critical displacement where there exist abrupt drop due to the brittle failure of the top CFRP facesheet. After the top skin failure, the densification of the core progresses until the indenter reaches the bottom skin and force-displacement response prior to top skin failure repeats for the SC. Whereas the densification is interrupted by the intermediate layer in DC and delays the failure. Analogous to the flexural loading and flatwise compression, the peak load of the indentation on DC is 41% higher than the SC.

Figure 4: a) Multi and single layered sandwich as manufactured, b) cross-section of indented multi-layer, c) cross-section of the indented single-layer sandwich. d) Force-displacement comparison of single core and double core sandwich.

In summary, the preliminary limited investigation carried out in this work of SC and DC points exposed that there exists a significant unrealized potential in sandwich structure morphology by varying the placement and stacking sequence of core when subjected to different static load conditions. Detailed

investigation of the damage and failure modes is necessary to assess the influence of various parameters, for example, the positioning of the second core relative to the first one.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Force-displacement response of sandwich structures with single and dual cores loaded in shear, flatwise compression and indentation are reported in this article. Across all the three load types tested, double-cored sandwich with middle layer displayed enhanced properties than their single-core counterpart. The enhancements of the double-core in the form of load resistance from lowest to greatest are 11%, 29% and 41% for line-load, out-of-plane compression and point loads. Whereas, the damage resistance estimated through the area under the curve until the maximum displacement of the single core marks 42%, 51% and 44% from TPBT, flatwise compression and quasi-static indentation.

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